

Human Reference Atlas

Standard Operating Procedure

Constructing Blood Vasculature-Organ Crosswalk Diagrams

Procedures for drawing diagrams to assist in developing the blood vasculature-organ crosswalk table

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Introduction

The procedures outlined in this document describe how to create diagrams to assist in developing the blood vasculature-organ crosswalk table. This crosswalk table is an essential part of the Human Reference Atlas's goal to build a Vasculature Common Coordinate Framework (VCCF), which uses vascular pathways to describe the location of cells throughout the body [Weber 2020]. The diagrams described in this standard operating procedure (SOP) enable domain experts to visualize and discuss the crosswalks, review them for accuracy, and suggest corrections. The primary audiences for this SOP are the authors and reviewers of the blood vasculature-organ crosswalk table, which is described in the SOP for [Authoring the Pathway Organ Crosswalk Tables](#).

Roles and Responsibilities

The **Illustrator** is responsible for constructing the draft diagram.

The **Reviewer** is a domain expert in blood vasculature or in an organ who reviews the diagrams and suggests corrections.

Table 1. Roles, names, and email addresses of key personnel.

Role	Name	Email
Illustrator	Katherine Gustilo Griffin Weber	katherine.gustilo@cuanschutz.edu weber@hms.harvard.edu
Reviewer	Varies based on organ	

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Procedures

Description of the diagram

Figure 1. This template illustrates the main parts and layout of the blood vasculature-organ crosswalk diagram.

Organ structures and blood vessels. The blood vasculature-organ crosswalk diagram (Figure 1) contains two types of objects. Overlapping rectangles represent the nested “partonomy” of anatomical structures in an organ, from gross anatomical structures on the macro- scale (on the left) down to functional tissue units on the micro- scale (on the right). Crossing through these rectangles are lines that represent blood vessels that supply, drain, or pass through those structures.

Blood vessel pathway loops. The diagram is distorted, compared to the actual shape of the organ, to straighten the blood vessels pathways as much as possible. In constructing these diagrams, the goal is to work towards a layout that looks similar to the template in Figure 1, with the main blood vasculature pathway drawn as a large loop. The loop starts in the upper left with the main artery supplying the organ and continues to the right, leading to smaller arteries, then arterioles, and finally reaching a capillary, which runs downwards on the right side of the diagram. At the bottom right of the diagram, the capillary connects to venules, which lead to veins, which leave the organ in the lower left of the diagram. Blood flow is typically clockwise through the diagram, with the arrow on the capillary pointing downwards. An exception is countercurrent flow, which is counterclockwise, with the arrow on the capillary pointing upwards and veins appearing above the arteries rather than below them.

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Multiple blood vessel pathways. There can be more than one blood vessel loop through the organ and loops can branch off of others. Each loop corresponds to a different vasculature pattern or tissue type. However, note that there might be many (i.e. millions) of instances of a single type of blood vessel pathway in an organ, but they are drawn as a single loop in this diagram. As a result, the total number of loops is typically less than ten and approximately equal to the number of FTUs in the organ.

Organ anatomical structures. Organ anatomical structures are placed around the straightened blood vessel pathway loops. As a result, structures that are near each other in the actual 3D anatomical shape of the organ might be separated in the diagram.

Note: This may initially look incorrect because it appears so different from typical illustrations of an organ. However, these diagrams are not intended to depict the relationships between organ anatomical structures. Instead, the focus is on the relationships between organ anatomical structures and the blood vessel pathways. This distorted view of the organ emphasizes that. By “unraveling” blood vessel pathways into simple loops, it highlights gaps where there are unknown parts of the blood vasculature. If an organ structure cannot be placed on one of the blood vessel loops, then it means the blood supply or drainage of the organ structure is unknown or the vessels are missing from the diagram. In contrast, in a traditional illustration of an organ, the blood vessel pathways are often broken up or unclear.

Usually larger organ structures (e.g., organ capsule, lobes, etc.) will be on the left side of the diagram with the larger blood vessels. Smaller structures (e.g., organ segments, FTUs) will be on the right with capillaries. A small vertical gap might appear near the middle of the diagram. On the left of this gap are large named structures and named blood vessels. On the right of the gap are smaller, repeated structures and blood vessels, which are not individually named.

Structures with an epithelial surface are the furthest on the right. A large downwards arrow on the right edge of the diagram indicates the fluid (or air) that flows past that epithelial surface. (One can also imagine this being where the “microbiome” of the organ lives.) Deeper layers in an organ are not as far to the right. Color distinguishes different types of tissues in the organ or highlights certain structures.

Create the diagram

- Select the organ.
- Collect the data.
 - Gather a list of blood vessels in that organ and their branching relationships from the blood-vasculature ASCT+B table.

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- Gather a list of anatomical structures in that organ and their nested partonomy from the organ's ASCT+B table. Suggest changes to ASCT+B tables as needed, see [SOP](#).
- Perform a literature review to obtain published information on blood vessels that supply, drain, overlap, or are part of the anatomical structures in the organ. This will form the initial draft crosswalk that will be illustrated in the diagram.
- Review the blood vasculature-organ crosswalk diagram PowerPoint [template slide](#) (Figure 1) and the diagrams that have previously been created for [other organs](#) as examples of what the diagrams should look like.
- Create a copy of the PowerPoint template slide as a starting point for the new organ.
- Draw each organ anatomical structure as a rectangle on the PowerPoint slide, replacing the examples in the copied template slide.
 - Show the nested partonomy by drawing the child structure as a smaller rectangle within the border of and in front of a larger rectangle representing the parent structure.
 - Label the anatomical structure using a text box either on or close to the rectangle.
- Draw each blood vessel as a line on the PowerPoint slide, replacing the examples in the copied template slide.
 - Show the branching relationships by placing the starting point of the child vessel either on or at the end of the line representing the parent vessel that it branches from.
 - Label the vessel using a text box placed close to the vessel line.
- Align objects so that blood vessel lines overlay rectangles representing the anatomical structures that they directly supply or drain, overlap, or are part of.
 - Place a text box with a question mark “?” and/or additional comments to note places where domain expert feedback is needed. For example, this might be an anatomical structure rectangle that has no vessel or a vessel for which the corresponding anatomical structures are not known.
- Use the following guidelines to layout and color the diagram. However, deviations are allowed in order to add clarity or to emphasize aspects of the diagram.
 - The overall layout of the diagram should aim to make the blood vessel paths as simple as possible.
 - Ideally, blood vessel paths should be shaped like the letter “U” rotated 90 degrees counterclockwise, with the major artery supplying the organ on the upper left, leading to a capillary that runs down the right side of the diagram, and ending with the major vein draining the organ on the lower left. Note that blood flows in a clockwise direction around the diagram.
 - Draw multiple “U” shaped paths if needed to represent different types of vascular loops in the organ. Avoid having paths cross as much as possible.

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- Place the organ anatomical structure rectangles in positions to reflect their relationship to the vessel paths, even if this greatly distorts how the anatomical structures are actually aligned with each other in the organ.
- Split the diagram, if needed, into “gross anatomical vasculature” on the left and “microvasculature” on the right. The rightmost anatomical structures and blood vessels should represent the functional tissue units (FTUs) in the organ.
- For organs with anatomical structures for epithelium, place the epithelium rectangles near the right side of the diagram. The space to the right of the epithelium represents the outside of the organ (or the inside of a hollow organ). Draw a vertical downward arrow in that space to illustrate the flow of air, fluid, etc., across the epithelial surface. Vertically flip vascular pathways that run in a countercurrent direction to the arrow (i.e., place the artery/arteriole below the vein/venule so that blood flows in a counterclockwise direction).
- Fill the anatomical structure rectangles with the following colors:
 - Use pale warm colors (e.g., yellow, pink and orange) for most rectangles; shades of gray to highlight connective tissue or an organ hilum; and pale cool colors (e.g., green) if needed to highlight epithelium, ducts, or FTUs.
 - Smaller nested structures should be darker than their larger parent structures. This effect can be achieved by either using a darker shade of color or by layering semi-transparent rectangles with the same color.
- Color and style the blood vessel lines in the following way:
 - Color arteries and arterioles in red; capillaries and portal veins in purple; and veins, venules, sinusoids, and sinuses in blue.
 - Use thicker lines for larger vessels.
 - Use solid lines for all vessels, except use dashed lines for fenestrated or sinusoidal capillaries.
 - Add arrows to vessel lines as needed to clarify the direction of blood flow. This is especially important for countercurrent flows.
 - Draw veins and venules behind and below arteries and arterioles.
- Align large vessels that are in multiple organ diagrams, such as the aorta, inferior/ superior vena cava, and hepatic portal vein, so that they are in the same horizontal position in each diagram. This allows different organ diagrams to “fit together”.

Review process

- Make a copy of the PowerPoint slide with the draft diagram.
- The Illustrator describes the diagram to the Reviewer and points out places where additional domain expertise is needed to complete the diagram.
- The Reviewer suggests corrections.
- The Illustrator modifies the copy of the diagram to reflect those changes.
- Repeat steps 3 and 4 as needed.

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- Modify the blood vasculature-organ crosswalk table to match the final diagram (see its [SOP](#) for details).
- Share the draft and final diagrams with the authors of the blood vasculature ASCT+B table and the organ ASCT+B table for comments and to ensure any missing anatomical structures are added to existing ASCT+B tables.

References and Resources

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Glossary

Anatomical structures: Parts of the body in defined locations and regions, including the surface, internal organs and tissues. These structures may be described by gross or microscopic morphology and include functional tissue units and highly organized cellular ecosystems (such as alveoli in the lungs).

ASCT+B Tables: Anatomical Structures, Cell Types and Biomarkers (ASCT+B) Tables are authored by multiple experts across many consortia. Tables capture the partonomy of anatomical structures, cell types and major biomarkers (e.g., gene, protein, lipid or metabolic markers).

Functional Tissue Unit (FTU): The smallest tissue organization that performs a unique physiologic function and is replicated multiple times in a whole organ.

Vascular Common Coordinate Framework (VCCF): A proposed approach to use vasculature as a coordinate system to map all the cells in the human body.

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